

Open Versus Closed Lateral Internal Sphincterotomy in Chronic Anal Fissures: A comparative study

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Abstract:

Background: Fissure-in-ano is a very common anal disorder which predominantly presents with severe pain. Lateral internal sphincterotomy remains the main treatment modality. This may be performed using open or closed method, each with their attendant complications. Aim of this study to evaluate the outcomes of open lateral internal sphincterotomy and closed lateral internal sphincterotomy with a cataract knife in terms of operation time, postoperative pain, faecal and flatus incontinence, and hospital stay.

Methods: A total of 100 patients with chronic anal fissure were enrolled in this study. Of these, 50 patients underwent open lateral sphincterotomy, and 50 underwent closed sphincterotomy. They were followed up for 8 months post-surgery. The results and complications of the two groups were compared and statistically analyzed.

Results: Post-operative complications such as pain, bleeding, infection, incontinence, and recurrence were compared between the two groups. Pain, bleeding, and incontinence to flatus were significantly lesser in the closed group ($P < 0.05$), while there was no difference in the incidence of infection and recurrence between the two groups.

Conclusion: In the treatment of chronic anal fissures, closed lateral internal sphincterotomy is superior than open sphincterotomy.

Keywords: Chronic Fissure, Closed Method, Lateral Sphincterotomy, Open Method.

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Introduction

A longitudinal ulcer in the anal canal is called as fissure in ano. It can be an acute anal fissure or chronic anal fissure. It is one of the benign painful conditions of anoderm, which is caused by raising internal sphincter spasm with impaired tissue perfusion. The classical vicious cycle formed by pain, and consequently, internal sphincter spasm that leads to fissure formation causes pain in anoderm. [1,2]

Hence, the aim of the treatment is to break this vicious cycle. Chronic fissures are characterized by sentinel tag, hypertrophic anal papillae, anal sphincter spasm, and fibrosis. In recumbent position, the chronic fissure is commonly seen posteriorly at 6 o' clock position and sometimes in 12 o' clock position. Chronic fissures are more difficult to treat conservatively. [3] There are many methods to relax the hypertonic internal anal sphincter such

as topical glyceryltrinitrate (0.2%), topical diltiazem, botulinum toxin injection, and surgical internal sphincterotomy. Among these methods, surgical sphincterotomy has the highest healing rate with low recurrence. [4-6]

There are various surgical methods of treatment of anal fissure such as anal dilatation, fissure excision, fissure excision with sphincterotomy, open lateral anal internal sphincterotomy and closed anal internal sphincterotomy. This study was designed to compare the results of the open and closed technique of lateral internal sphincterotomy with reference to post-operative complications and outcomes.

Material and Methods

From April 2023 to March 2024, this prospective clinical trial was conducted in the General Surgery Department of Narayan Medical College and Hos-

pital, Jamuhar, Sasaram, Bihar. The study included 100 patients with chronic anal fissure, all patients of both sexes between the ages of 20 and 50 years' old who presented to our surgical unit with a chronic anal fissure. Patients were excluded if they had undergone any other anorectal procedure at the time of anal sphincterotomy, or if they had a history of sphincterotomy or anal dilatation in the past. Fissures associated with inflammatory bowel illness or cancer were also ruled out. All patients were admitted to NMCH, Surgical Ward and given a full medical history and physical examination. The patient was then placed in the lithotomy, lateral (side) or Jack-knife positions, and a local inspection of the anal region was performed to see the sites of anal fissure, induration (acute, chronic), skin tag, bleeding, and digital palpation (PR) of the anus. Investigations were completed (HB, WBCs, GUE, FBS, CXR, ECG, etc.).

Only patients with chronic anal fissure were included in our study, and all patients undergoing surgery were divided into two groups: group-A included Underwent surgery using the open method; in the operating room, each patient was given two cards, one written closed and the other written open, and lateral internal sphincterotomy was performed in 50 (50 percent) of patients using the closed method (Group A) and 50 (50 percent) of patients using the open method (Group B). A detailed history and physical examination were used to evaluate and diagnose these patients as having chronic anal fissures. These Individuals Position of

Lithotomy After making a 1 cm incision in the 3 o'clock position, the Internal Sphincterotomy was clearly identified. Curved Artery Forceps were used to hook the sphincter segment, which was then divided using electrocautery or scissors. Then, for a few minutes, pressure was maintained to ensure good hemostasis. Secondary Intention was used to keep the wound open for healing. An Anal Retractor was used to retract the anal canal in Group B.

The Internal Sphincter Has a Tight Band Feel to It. Palpation revealed the Intersphincteric Groove. To enter the Intersphincteric Groove, an 11-size Scalpel was inserted through the perianal skin at 3 o'clock. Hemostasis was achieved by applying pressure for a few minutes. About 13 to 12 percent of the internal sphincter was divided in both methods. Patients were followed for 8 months after surgery to assess outcomes and complications such pain, bleeding, infection, incontinence, and recurrence. SPSS Software Version was used to conduct the statistical analysis. The Statistical Significance of Results Was Analyzed Using the Chi-Square Test. Statistical significance is defined as a P value of less than 0.05.

Results

One hundred patients with chronic anal fissure were chosen for this study from those who were presented in surgical out patients department of NMCH, Sasaram, Bihar between April 2023 and March 2024.

Table1 : Age distribution of patients

Age in years	Number of patients	Percentage
20-30	25	25%
31-40	40	40%
41-50	35	35%
Total	100	100%

25 patients (25%) were between 20 - 30 years, 40 patients (40%) were between 31 - 40 years and 35 patients (35%) were between 41 - 50 years of age.

Table 2: Sex distributions

Sex	Number of patients	Percentage
Male	68	68%
Female	32	32%
Total	100	100%

There were 68 male patients (68%) and 32 female patients (32%) with ratio of 2.1:1 respectively.

Table 3: Site of fissure

Site of fissure	Number of patients	Percentage
Posterior	90	90%
Anterior	10	10%
Others	00	00%
Total	100	100%

In all 100 patients included in the study, the position of anal fissure was noted. Ninety patients (90%) were having posterior midline fissure and 10 patients (10%) were having anterior fissure (Table3).

Table 4: Mode of presentation

Chief complaint	No. of patients	Percentage
Painful defecation	62	62%
Bleeding PR	35	35%
Perianal swelling	02	02%
Pruritus in Ano	01	01%
Total	100	100%

The chief complaint of most of patients was pain on defecation. Out of 100 patients, 62 patients (62%) complained of pain during and after defecation thirty-five of patients (35%) had the chief complaint of bleeding per rectum, the bleeding was usually of small amount and occurred at the time of defecation, 2 patients (2%) also presented with perianal swelling and 1 patient (1%) pruritus in ano (Table 4).

Table 5: Post-operative discharge

	Closed	Percentage	Open	Percentage
POD1	35	70%	05	10%
POD2	10	20%	10	20%
POD3	03	06%	30	60%
POD4	02	04%	5	10%
Total	50	100%	50	100%

Out of 50 patients 35 patients (70%) discharged on post-operative day 1, ten patients (20%) day 2, three patients (6%) day 3 and two patients (4%) on day 4 respectively in closed methods, whereas in open methods day 1 five patients (10%), day 2 ten patients (20%) day 3 thirty patients (60%) and day 4 five patients (10%) respectively.

Table 6: Complications of lateral internal sphincterotomy

	Closed	Percentage	Open	Percentage
Pain	01	02%	06	12%
Bleeding	02	04%	08	16%
Infection	01	02%	03	06%
Incontinence	03	09%	10	20%
Recurrence	02	04%	02	04%
Total	09	18%	29	58%

Out of 50 patients nine patients (18%) developed complications in closed method and in open method 29 patients (58%) developed complications (Table 6).

Discussion

Most of the fissures were found in middle age group. 40% of the patients were between 31-40 years and mean age in present study was 35 years. Mean age reported in different studies range from 30 - 45 years which is the same of our study. In our study 68% of patients were males, and 32% of patients were females with a sex ratio of 2.1:1 respectively. In the study done by Nahas, 70% were males and 30% were females had chronic anal fissure with a ratio of 2.3:1. 55.2% males and 47.8% females with a ratio of 1.15:1 presented with chronic anal fissure in the study done by Melange.⁷⁻¹⁵

The patients suffering from anal fissure complain of pain, bleeding per rectum, discharge and pruritus and 62% patients presented with pain during or after defecation and 35% patients presented with bleeding, while in the other studies which was very close to the 45.4% and 35.7% respectively reported by Hanel et al. In our study 90 patients (90%) presented with posterior midline fissures and 10 patients (10%) presented with anterior anal fis-

sure. Mazier et al described that (84%) of anal fissures are more common posterior. Cushieri also described that (88%) most of the fissures are posterior midline. Nahas reported 86.1% posterior midline and 13.9% anterior fissure.⁷ This may be due to hypovascularization and hypo perfusion occur in the posterior anal commissure. Combination of these factors with internal anal sphincter hypertonia, causing ischemia, that explain the poor wound healing and the pain is ischemic in nature, occurs only for a certain period after defecation, Patients may try to avoid defecation because of the pain.¹⁵ In patients, undergoing closed lateral internal sphincterotomy, 41 (82%) out of 50 patients were free of symptoms while in open lateral internal sphincterotomy, 21 (42%) out of 50 patients were free of symptoms, Matikainen has described the similar results (50%) in case of closed lateral internal sphincterotomy.⁷

In this study, when the results of closed and open techniques were compared regarding pain (1 vs 6) that mean in closed technique less tissue dissection and in the closed method cause less bleeding than open (2 vs 8) due to less tissue damage, infection (1 vs 3), incontinence (3 vs 10) due to there is partial cutting of internal sphincter in both methods and its minor type (flatus incontinence), and recurrence (2 vs 2). However, in other studies like, Per-

nikoff, Salvati, Eisentat, Kortbeek, Langevin, Khoo had concluded in their study that closed lateral internal sphincterotomy for chronic anal fissure is effective and may result in significantly less post-operative discomfort, shorter postoperative stay and a less rate of complications compared with the open lateral internal sphincterotomy. 7,13,16,18,20

Conclusion

Closed lateral internal sphincterotomy can be used as a treatment of choice for chronic anal fissure. It is effective and safe with lower rates of complication than open sphincterotomy technique.

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